

THE COMPARATIVE DESCRIPTIONS OF UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LEXICONS.

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Annotation: The lexicon of Uzbek and Russian languages differs, first of all, by the fact that these languages belong to genetically different families. Although Uzbek is typologically included in the Altaic language family by many scholars as an agglutinative language, genetically it belongs to a group of Turkic languages that form a separate family. All Turkic and Uzbek words form the basis of the lexical richness of our language. Russian, on the other hand, belongs to the Slavic group of the Indo-European language family, both typologically and genetically, so it is based on all-Slavic and Old Russian words.

Keywords: translation, annotated dictionary, comparison, preferred variant, classification of phrases, russian commentary, uzbek language.

Introduction. The lexicon of both languages has undergone various events during its historical development, and their lexical structure consists of words borrowed from different languages. For example, Uzbek has many Persian-Tajik and Arabic words, while Russian has many European words. The vocabulary of the Uzbek language is mainly:

- common Turkish words (me, we, head, mountain one, two, mother, father ...)
- Uzbek words (worker, work, peace, youth, warrior, knowledge ...) - Arabic words (information, school, culture, literature, truth ...)
- Persian-Tajik words (sun, flower, napkin, dutar, tree ...)
- consists of layers such as words (airplane, computer, novel, designer, bus, trolleybus, drama ...). Lexical layers of the Russian language:
 - common Slavic words: дом, город, голова, мат, отец, брат, ден...
 - Old Russian languages: galka, snegopad, добрыу, potolok...
 - original Russian words: учитель, водитель, зарплата, раздевалка, зажигалка...
 - words learned from other languages: blouse, loaf (Polish), watermelon, kazna (Turkish), gramota, laurel (Greek), illusion, compote (French), train station, tram (English), opera, duet (Spanish)), and etc

According to the latest statistics, in the modern Uzbek literary language, words borrowed from Russian and other languages through this language are about 50%. Russian words in the lexicon of our language are used as active words in both scientific and technical literature and in oral speech. However, there are some differences between the Russian words and the Russian words, which are

reflected in the following: Phonetic differences Russian words that entered the Uzbek language in historical periods, ie until the beginning of the XX century, differ from the original Uzbek words in their pronunciation due to certain phonetic changes and Uzbekization. and is expressed in accordance with the pronunciation in the text. Examples include words like brush, brush, blanket, strawberry, rum, church. These pronunciations are the norm for modern Uzbek literary language. However, the words that came into our language relatively later, regardless of how they are pronounced in Uzbek speech, have retained the phonetic structure of the Russian language in the literary language: [istol] table, [ustul] chair, [ishkop] cupboard, [doctor] doctor, [melissa] police, [car] car, [bank] bank and so on. A number of new words have been created in the Uzbek language on the basis of borrowed words: tractor driver, classmate, gasifier, aircraft builder, costumer, athlete, computer operator, etc.

The phonetic and orthographic features of such words are also in line with Russian language norms. The lexical structure of the Russian language also includes Uzbek, Forstojik and Arabic words, almost all of which have undergone phonetic changes, so the pronunciation and spelling of such words in Uzbek and Russian are difficult. There are certain differences between: watermelon, arka, tovar, kazna, uryuk, fig, kishlak, karagach, saxaul, lagman, manty, pilaf and so on. Semantic differences. In Uzbek dialects, the meaning is narrowed, expanded or changed. For example, the word pen has three meanings in Russian, such as a hand (small hand), a handle, and a writing instrument, while in Uzbek the word is used only in the sense of a writing instrument. If the word "pocket", which was acquired from the Russian language, deviated from its true meaning in the Russian language and acquired a completely different meaning in the Uzbek language (money bag). , the word samovar has an additional meaning in Uzbek - teahouse - in addition to the meaning of a single teapot in Russian. The meanings of Uzbek and Russian words do not always correspond in quantity in both languages. For example, the word "read" in Uzbek means both "read" and "learn". In Russian, these two meanings are represented by two different words (chitat, uchit). SI Ojegov's explanatory dictionary gives 24 meanings of the word idti, and the word to go in Uzbek has six meanings, according to the Uzbek Explanatory Dictionary. Similarly, in OTIL, the word exit has 22 meanings, while the Russian word vyyti has 7 meanings. In general, ambiguity is characteristic of words in both languages, most of which belong to the oldest lexical layers in both Uzbek and Russian. In some cases, the main and derivative meanings of polysemantic words in Uzbek correspond exactly to those in Russian. For

example: a gold ring - zolotoe koltso, golden autumn - zolotaya osen, golden hands - zolotye ruki or iron door - jeleznyaya dver, iron iroda - jeleznyaya volya. The words gold and iron in the given examples retain their main and derivative meanings even in the compounds translated from Russian into Uzbek. However, such an identity does not always arise in translation. Sometimes the main lexical meanings of words expressing the same concept are the same as in the Uzbek and Russian norms, but the new meanings formed from them do not correspond to each other in the two languages. For example, in Uzbek the handle of the pot is similar in shape to the ear, and in Uzbek this concept is also called ear. The Russians use the word pen in the sense of a handle, and the phrase "uxo kotla" sounds completely illogical and ridiculous in Russian. Similarly, in Russian, compounds such as nos korablya ("ship's nose"), gluxaya noch ("deaf night") do not exist in our language, and we use, of course, other words here: ship's bow, silent night . Therefore, when comparing the lexicon of Russian and Uzbek languages, it is better to use larger units, more precisely, sentences and texts, rather than words.

Phraseology. It is well-known that the oral tradition of the people is passed down from ancestor to generation, living, improving, expanding and enriching over the centuries. The Uzbek language is rich in various phrases, proverbs and phrases, which reflect the history, culture, traditions and spirituality of our people.

We call lexical units that consist of two or more words and have a single meaning a phrase or phraseological units or phraseological units. Phrases are usually interpreted as units equivalent to one word (lexeme). It is true that the units that make up a stable combination, that is, a phrase, basically represent a single meaning, a concept, but there are more colors and reliefs than in the lexeme. Therefore, lexical meaning cannot be equated with phraseological meaning. Otherwise, we wouldn't be using phrases to express a concept. As in all languages, the lexical structure of the Russian language contains phrases, which are used in speech with different meanings and meanings. The structure and content of phrases in Uzbek and Russian languages, when compared, it is determined that there are the following similarities between them:

- 1) In both languages, phrases consist of two or more words: - показать кузькину мать;
- 2) Equivalent to a phrase or sentence: One comes from the garden and the other comes from the mountain. - Один про Фому, а другой про Ерёму; (Not the exact translation of the phrases, but the Russian equivalents are given here.)

3) In both languages, the phrases are in the form of a single lexical unit and the word in them cannot be changed.

4) In both languages, phraseological units can come in a syntactic task: He always wags his tail in front of leaders. - Он всегда вертит хвостом перед начальниками.

5) In both languages, phrases are not formed in the process of speech, but live in the language as a ready-made linguistic unit. When semantically comparing phraseological units in Uzbek and Russian languages, the following cases are observed: Some Uzbek phrases correspond to Russian phrases both in form and meaning: they do not hurt the fly - и мухи не обидит, to care like the pupil of the eye - беречь как зеницу ока, the top hair is straight - волосы дыбом;

Conclusion. The phenomena of formality, ambiguity, semantics, and ambiguity are common to all linguistic expressions, as are all lexical units. For example, the Russian phrase "пускают петуха" is used both in the sense of "giving a thin sound in the process of singing" and "to set fire to, to throw ashes into the sky", and these two meanings of there is a formative relationship between. The term "слонят голову" is ambiguous, as it is used to mean "to lose, to lose," and "to bow." The phrases "Засучив рукава" (sleeve rolling) and "в поте лица" (sweating) create a relationship of meaning in the Russian language, while "с открытой душой открыто" (openly) and "с камнем за пазухой" (hiding a stone behind his back) creates a spiritual contradiction.

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